

IR⁴ and mass⁸ spectra of alcohols led confirmation of the compounds as hentriacontanol-1 which was confirmed by direct comparison m.m.p. with authentic sample 84°–85°.

The colourless needles, m.p. 144°–145°, from the bark of *T. undulata* gave positive Liebermann-Burchard test for sterol. Its IR spectra showed absorption at 3400 cm⁻¹ (–OH stretching). The identity of sterol as ϵ -sitosterol was confirmed by preparation of its acetate⁶ (Acetic anhydride/pyridine). m.p. 128°.

The colourless compounds, m.p. 134°–135°, from the barks of *H. adenophyllum* and *M. hortensis* gave positive Liebermann-Burchard test for sterol. The identity of sterol as β -sitosterol was confirmed by its mixed melting points, I.R. spectrum and its acetate⁶. m.p. 128°.

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References

1. PARUP SINGH, LALIT PRAKASH and KRISHNA C. JOSHI. *Phytochem.* 1972, 11, 1498.
2. R. A. BROWN, W. S. YOUNG and N. NICOLAIDES. *Anal. Chem.*, 1954, 26, 1653.
3. H. EL KHADIM and M. M. ABDEL RAHMAN. *J. Chem. Soc.*, (London), 1965, 3483.
4. M. TASUMI and T. SHIMANOUCHI. *Spectrochim. Acta*, 1964, 20, 629.
5. I. HEILBRON and H. M. BUNBURY, Dictionary of Organic Compounds London: Eyre and spottiswoode 1953, 4, 362.
6. KRISHNA C. JOSHI and L. B. SINGH. *Z. Naturforsch.*, 1970, 25b, 270.

Spectrophotometric studies of the Chelates of Iron(III) with 2-Hydroxy-5-methyl Acetophenone Semicarbazone Systems

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THE chelating tendencies of 2-hydroxy phenone semicarbazones have not been investigated fully. Our laboratory has been interested in studying the chelating properties of 2-hydroxy phenones and their derivatives. As a part of this program it was considered worth while to explore the analytical potentiality of 2-hydroxy phenone semicarbazones.

The present note describes the results of spectro photometric studies of the green ($\lambda_{max} = 600$ nm) coloured solution formed when iron(III) react with alcoholic solution of 2-hydroxy-5-methylacetophenone semicarbazone and the colourless complexes formed by iron(III) with oxalate and diamino-ethane tetra-acetate ions at low pH using 2-hydroxy-5-methyl-acetophenone semicarbazone as an auxiliary ligand

Experimental

2-Hydroxy-5-methyl acetophenone (m.p. 49°) was prepared by Fries migration of the corresponding phenyl acetate using anhydrous aluminium chloride in the absence of solvent. The 2-hydroxy-5-methyl acetophenone semicarbazone (5MeOAS; m.p. 212°) was obtained as pale yellow crystals by refluxing 1 : 1 mole of 2-hydroxy-5-methyl acetophenone and semicarbazide hydrochloride in methanol for 1.5 hr. The product was purified by recrystallization from hot acetic acid. Standard solutions were prepared by dissolving weighed amounts of the reagent in pure methanol

All other chemicals used were of A.R. quality. The stock solutions of iron(III), ammonium oxalate, and Na₂EDTA were prepared by dissolving a calculated amount of each in 0.01M nitric acid. The concentrations of iron (III) and oxalate in solution were determined by standard gravimetric and volumetric methods. Dilute solutions of desired concentrations were obtained, as and when needed, using these stock solutions. All aqueous solutions were prepared in water twice distilled over alkaline permanganate in all glass pyrex unit.

Spectrophotometric measurements were made on Beckman DU spectrophotometer, using 1 cm glass cells. All measurements were carried out at 30° ± 0.5° in a 50% methanol–50% water (v/v) medium adjusted to 0.005M with respect to nitric acid.

Results and Discussion

The nature of complexes was determined by the method of Vosburgh and Cooper¹. The observations showed that only one complex with λ_{max} of 600 nm is formed in the system. The composition of the complex was determined by Job's method² using equimolar and non-equimolar solutions, slope-ratio method³ and molar-ratio method⁴. It was found to be 1 : 1 in all the cases. The apparent stability constant $\log K = 5.3 \pm 0.1$ of the complex was calculated from absorbance data by the method of Mukherji and Dey⁵.

Colourless complexes of iron(III) :

The method used here have been described earlier by Babko *et al.*^{6,7}. In this method a solution containing Fe(5MeOAS)⁺² ($1 \times 10^{-4}M$) was prepared by mixing equal volumes of iron(III) ($2 \times 10^{-4}M$) and 5MeOAS ($1 \times 10^{-3}M$). The continuous variation⁸

studies were than carried out using equimolar solutions ($1 \times 10^{-4} M$) of $\text{Fe}(5\text{MeOAS})^{+2}$ and Na_2EDTA /ammonium oxalate. The absorbances were measured at the λ_{max} (600 nm) of the $\text{Fe}(5\text{MeOAS})^{+2}$. Two sets of solutions, one with and the other without Na_2EDTA /ammonium oxalate were prepared. The difference in the absorbance of the pair of corresponding solutions for the two sets corresponds to the Y function in the Job's curve. The maximum de-colourization was observed at a ratio of iron(III) : Na_2EDTA /ammonium oxalate = 1 : 1. This indicates the formation of a complex corresponding to the formula $\text{FeEDTA}^-/\text{Fe C}_2\text{O}_4^{+}$ under the experimental conditions used.

References

1. W. C. VOSBURGH and G. R. COOPER, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1941, **63**, 437.
2. P. JOB, *Ann. Chim.*, 1928, **9**, 113.
3. A. E. HARVEY and D. L. MANNING, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, **72**, 4488.
4. J. H. YOE and A. L. JONES, *Ind. Eng. Chem. Anal. Ed.*, 1944, **16**, 111.
5. A. K. MUKHERJI and A. K. DEY, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1958, **6**, 324.
6. A. K. BABKO and K. E. KTEINER, *J. Gen. Chem.*, 1947, **17**, 1259.
7. A. K. BABHO and L. I. DUBOVENKO, Soviet Research on Complex and Coordination Compounds. Part III, p. 914.

On the use of Methyl Alcohol as a Solvent for Bromine in Kinetic Studies

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RECENTLY^{1,2,3}, the kinetics and mechanism of the addition of bromine to compounds containing an ethylenic double bond have been investigated, using anhydrous and aqueous acetic acids as solvents. However, our attempts to make similar kinetic investigations using methyl alcohol as solvent were not quite successful since solutions of bromine in methyl alcohol are unstable due to the formation of methyl hypobromite. Recently Seth and Bose⁴ have studied the kinetics of the bromination of cinnamic acid and its derivatives in methyl alcohol as solvent. In the present paper, we are therefore reporting our findings regarding the stability of bromine in methyl alcohol.

It has been observed^{5,6} that, in a solution of bromine in methyl alcohol, methyl hypobromite is formed according to the equilibrium

When an ethylenic compound reacts with bromine in methyl alcohol, two products, are formed *viz.*, the dibromide and the methoxy bromide, although different proposals have been made regarding the mechanism of formation of these products^{6,7}. In fact Bartlett and Trabell⁷ found that, in the reaction between stilbene and bromine in methyl alcohol, the fraction of methoxy bromide in the products was about 83% in the presence of 0.2M sodium bromide and 99% in the absence of added bromide. The above observations by Bartlett and Tarbell⁷ and by Meinel⁶ are consistent with our findings (see experimental section below) which clearly show that a solution of bromine in methyl alcohol is unstable. The assumption of Seth and Bose⁴ that, in the bromination of cinnamic acid (and its derivatives) in methyl alcohol, the only product is dibromo-cinnamic acid is therefore not valid.

Experimental

A standard solution of bromine in acetic acid was prepared. 5 ml of the bromine solution was added to a known but fixed amount of methyl alcohol taken in a groundglass-stoppered tube (capacity 20 ml) which was also provided with a cup at its mouth, similar to that in an iodine-flask. After allowing the bromine to react with the methyl alcohol for a known duration of time in a thermostat at 30°, potassium iodide solution (10%) was added and the liberated iodine was titrated against standard sodium thiosulphate (0.01N). It is to be noted that, in this method, the loss of bromine due to volatility⁸ is less than 1%. Further details of the experimental technique and the purification of the acetic acid are given in earlier papers from this laboratory^{8,9}.

Results are given in Table 1. The first eight entries are for B.D.H. Analar methyl alcohol, using 10 ml of the alcohol in each case. The remaining entries are for methyl alcohol (20 ml in each case) obtained by purifying a commercial sample by

TABLE 1--RESULTS SHOWING THE INSTABILITY OF BROMINE IN METHYL ALCOHOL

Duration for which Br_2 was allowed to react with methyl alcohol min.	Decrease in $[\text{Br}_2]$ %
0	—
10	4.5
25	10.0
43	16.0
60	22.0
79	26.5
97	31.5
119	36.0
0	—
30	23.7
100	54.2
130	62.6
310	75.3